

17-21 Julio 2023 – Donostia

2nd Basque Conference on Cyber Physical Systems and Artificial Intelligence

Proposing *High Technology developments*
in *Low Cost solutions*

E. Irigoyen

- 1. Context**
- 2. Objective**
- 3. Study**
- 4. Results**
- 5. Final conclusions**

Department of Systems Engineering and Automatic Control

Motivation:

Create technologically advanced solutions in order to facilitate the style of life of people with disabilities.

Colaborating in projects coming from county and national calls

- ❑ Karmele López de Ipiña (2004):
 - Developments of Intelligent Tutoring Systems

Laguntxo

- ❑ Manuel Graña (2007):
 - Part of the Research Group **GIC**

A type – Research Group

Main objective:

To apply techniques developed in the Intelligent Control field into assistive solutions focused on users and responsables (medicians, relatives, etc.)

Artificial Neural Networks

Fuzzy Logic

Finite-states Machines

Reinforcement Learning

Cardiovascular Rehabilitation

- **Proposal:**
 - **Modeling of the bicycle-person binomial to obtain an advanced control to prevent and treat cardiovascular problems.**

Identification of emotions & stress

- **Proposal:**

- To design a system for the detection and classification of emotional changes by analyzing non-intrusive physiological signals.

ECG

GSR

- The resolution of a **3D-wooden puzzle** within a limited time.
- Different puzzles to provoke different levels of stress.

Upper limb motor functions

- **Proposal:**
 - Neuro-fuzzy multi-surface electrode models for hand grasping.

Reinforcement Learning

Robust classification of stress

- **Proposal:**
 - Improve and strengthen stress classification algorithms, together with their implementation in Low Cost platforms.

Relevant physiological signals in the study of stress

Electrocardiogram (ECG) Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) Breathing (RSP)

Detection of heart disease - BP

Development of a first prototype based on a low-cost platform.

- **Proposal:**
 - **Design and development of a system to support the diagnosis and identification of pathologies implemented with low-cost devices.**

Contacto seco

Contacto húmedo

Developments:

- Sensors
- Platforms
- Data Bases
- Communication
- Processing

Sensors:

- *PulsiOx*
- *GSR*
- *ECG*

	Señal Pulsioxímetro	Señal GSR	Señal ECG
Frecuencia de muestreo	10 Hz	1 Hz	100 Hz

Platforms:

- ESP32
- R-Pi

Signal processing:

- *Comunication*
- *Filtering*
- *Visualization*

2023-01-23 09:52:25.806	127208	128299
2023-01-23 09:52:25.906	127163	128317
2023-01-23 09:52:26.006	127210	128362
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2023-01-23 08:25:58.506	150808	158081

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Thank you for your attention!

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